

THE ROLE OF THE BURROW STRUCTURE IN THE CHARACTERISATION OF TRAP DOOR SPIDERS *NEMESIA* AUDOUIN, 1826 (ARANEAE, MYGALOMORPHAE)

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ABSTRACT

Three new species of the trap-door spider genus *Nemesia* Audouin, 1826 are described from southern Portugal, namely *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. from Portimão and Alvor, *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. from Castelão (Loulé), and *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. from Odeleite. These species have specific morphological and/or behavioural similarities with *N. athiasi* Franganillo, 1920, *N. fagei* Frade & Bacelar, 1931, and *N. ungoliant* Decae, Cardoso & Selden, 2007, but are easily distinguishable if attention is paid to all details including the size, the prosoma shape and the burrow structure. The available literature on *N. fagei* is discussed and the need to consider the burrow as a possible character for diagnosis when describing and identifying species of the genus *Nemesia* is illustrated. Finally, a few guidelines are proposed to aid in the study of these spiders, both at the species level and for the general understanding of spiders of this genus.

Keywords. Algarve, diversity, new species, Southern of Portugal, trapdoor spiders.

RESUMEN

El papel de la estructura del nido en la caracterización de las especies de arañas de trampilla *Nemesia* Audouin, 1826 (Araneae, Mygalomorphae)

Se describen tres nuevas especies de arañas del género *Nemesia* Audouin, 1826 del sur de Portugal: *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. de Portimão y Alvor, *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. de Castelão (Loulé), y *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. de Odeleite. Estas especies presentan ciertas similitudes morfológicas y/o comportamentales con *N. athiasi* Franganillo, 1920, *N. fagei* Frade & Bacelar, 1931, y *N. ungoliant* Decae, Cardoso & Selden 2007, pero son fácilmente distinguibles si se presta atención a todos los detalles incluyendo el tamaño, la forma del prosoma y la estructura de la madriguera. Se discute la literatura disponible sobre *N. fagei* y se ilustra la necesidad de considerar la madriguera como un posible carácter para el diagnóstico al describir e identificar especies del género *Nemesia*. Finalmente, se proponen algunas pautas destinadas a ayudar en el estudio de estas arañas a nivel de identificación y comprensión tanto a nivel específico como a nivel general de las arañas de este género.

Palabras clave. Algarve, arañas tramperas, diversidad, nuevas especies, sur de Portugal.

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Introduction

Trapdoor spiders (infraorder Mygalomorphae) inhabit burrows with a lid at the entrance, which is used to hide from prey and predators (Buchli, 1969). This cryptic behaviour and the close morphological similarities among the different species (Bond *et al.*, 2006) make them a challenging group to study. One of the most diverse mygalomorph genera is *Nemesia* Audouin, 1826, with 73 valid species inhabiting all terrestrial habitats in the Mediterranean Basin (Decae, 2012; World Spider Catalog, 2024). According to the World Spider Catalog, currently six species have been recorded in Portugal: *Nemesia athiasi* Franganillo, 1920, *N. bacelarae* Decae, Cardoso & Selden, 2007, *N. berlandi* Frade & Bacelar, 1931, *N. fagei* Frade & Bacelar, 1931, *N. uncinata* Bacelar, 1933, and *N. ungoliant* Decae, Cardoso & Selden, 2007. It has been suggested that the diversity of burrow constructions and associated mechanisms exhibited by the genus could aid species identification (Mora, 2015: 31, 76, 304). These include structures likely aimed at diminishing predatory attacks, such as external plugs

to block the entrance —e.g., *N. fagei*—, or burrows with two independent openings —e.g., *N. athiasi*.

The first aim of this work is to describe three new species of *Nemesia* based on their morphology and biology, including their burrow structures. The second aim is to investigate whether differences in carapace shape (i.e., circularity) can be helpful for species identification and to reveal differences in their ecology.

Material and methods

SAMPLING METHODS AND SPECIMENS

Burrows were searched near the roots of shrubs and trees, especially on slopes with low vegetation density. All specimens were collected by cautiously digging around the burrow, avoiding damage to the spider and studying the internal structures of the burrow. A total of 26 specimens were collected by hand: nine from Alvor and Portimão —6.7 km apart—, eight from Castelão (Loulé) —39.4 km between Portimão and Castelão—, and nine from Odeleite — 47.2 km between Castelão and Odeleite— (Fig. 1; Table 1),

Fig. 1. Locations sampled in south Portugal. Alvor, black square, 1; Portimão, black circle, 2; Castelão (Loulé), black triangle, 3; and Odeleite, black star, 4.

Fig. 1. Localidades muestreadas en el sur de Portugal. Alvor, cuadrado negro, 1; Portimão, círculo negro, 2; Castelão (Loulé), triángulo negro, 3; and Odeleite, estrella negra, 4.

with spiders exhibiting morphological differences among localities. Careful examination of the specimens and comparison with previously described species revealed that they represent three new species.

Table 1. Sampling localities.

Tabla 1. Localidades de muestreo.

Locality	Longitude	Latitude	Elevation (m)
Alvor	37.120525	-8.564457	18
Portimão	37.173450	-8.528514	5
Loulé, Castelão	37.177570	-8.084661	132
Odeleite	37.322378	-7.580936	180

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY

The left leg II of two specimens from each population was severed and conserved in alcohol 96° for future molecular analyses. Following the procedures of previous publications, the morphological study of spiders and their photographs were conducted using an E31SPM20000KPA ocular camera mounted on an Euromex SB 1903-p stereomicroscope (Luis de la Iglesia, 2019; Pertegal & Pinilla-Rosa, 2023). Most specimens were mature females, so they were dissected with microdissection scissors and a hypodermic needle to study their spermathecae. The software ToupView was used to take measurements (in millimetres), and ImageJ to estimate the shape of the carapace.

ABBREVIATIONS

Collections. MNHNC = Museu Nacional de História Natural e Da Ciencia; CCPP = Collection Cristian Pertegal Pérez.

Morphology. BL+ch = body length with chelicerae; BL = body length; Ca = caput length; Ch = caput height; CL = carapace length; CW = carapace width; Th = thorax height; Cir = $4\pi \cdot \text{area} / \text{perimeter}^2$, a value of 1.0 indicates a perfect circle; as the value approaches 0.0, it indicates an increasingly elongated shape (eq1); Cly = clypeus length; AER = anterior eye row width; PER = posterior eye row width; ALE = anterior lateral eye length; PLE = posterior lateral eye length; AME = anterior median eye length; PME = posterior median eye length; El = eye group length; POP = pattern of the deep black pigmentation on the ocular process; Ml = maxillae length; Mw = maxillae width; Ll = labium length; Lw = labium width; Sl = sternum length; Sw = sternum width; Spwt = top section of spermatheca width; Spwring = ring of glandular tissue length; Spwm = middle section of spermatheca width; Splenght = spermathecae length; Spdistint = distance between the internal side of spermathecae; Spdistext = distance between the external side of spermathecae; Ta = tarsus length; Me = metatarsus length; Til = tibia length; Pa = patella length; Fe = femur length; PSP =

number of prolateral spines of patella; RSP = number of retrolateral spines of patella; MTF4 ratio = relative lengths of metatarsus, tibia and femur of leg IV; PLS = posterior lateral spinnerets; PMS = posterior median spinnerets.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Differences in shape and size among specimens were evaluated using the circularity index (eq.1). A GLM test in which species identity and carapace width were included as independent variables and circularity as the dependent variable was compared using AIC with another model not including carapace width (i.e., body size). The more complex model (i.e., with more parameters) was considered as the best model, only if AIC values were two units below the simpler model. Finally, the GLM was tested for significance using a log-likelihood ratio test. The function “glm” in R package “stats” and the function “Anova” in the R library “car” were used for this analysis.

Results

Taxonomy

Nemesia bonali sp. nov.

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Figs 2–5

DIAGNOSIS

The spermathecae of *N. bonali* sp. nov. is columnar with a narrow ring of glandular tissue before the globular end of ducts (Fig. 2A–C). The morphology of these structures in combination with others less conspicuous structures, along with burrow structures, allow to differentiate this species from other *Nemesia* species. The species with a more similar spermathecae morphology is *N. athiasi*, characterised by prolateral and retrolateral spines on patellae III and IV, with the possibility of spines on the patellae of palps and legs I and II, prosoma covered with black and white pubescence, POP covering the eye group, shallow fovea, club-shaped cuspules and maculae on legs. *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. has patellar spines only in the prolateral zone of palps and legs II, prosoma with low density of pubescence, POP in AME and each group of ALE, PLE and PME, deep furrow in fovea, conical cuspules and lack of maculae on the legs. *Nemesia athiasi* builds a branched burrow with two stiff trapdoors of the same size and morphology, while *N. bonali* sp. nov. builds a simple burrow with a somewhat flexible lid—also, the burrows of *N. athiasi* lack a plug. The redescription of *N. fagei* provided by Decae *et al.* (2007) allows for differentiation of this species from *N. bonali* sp. nov. by the carapace size—*N. bonali* sp. nov. has a larger carapace than *N. fagei* (6.09–6.96 vs. 3.7–5.2 mm of carapace length)—, the

elevation of caput—elevated in *N. bonali* sp. nov. and only slightly elevated in *N. fagei*—, the lack of a dark marking on the carapace, the central groove of the fovea on the prosoma, and the absence of maculae on the proximal segment of PMS of *N. fagei*. The original description of *N. fagei* is based on a single female, whose main differences with *N. bonali* sp. nov. are the total size —16 mm length—, carapace length —8.5 mm—, prosoma shape —more circular than the new species (the distal edge of the prosoma of *N. fagei* is 2/3 the width of the frontal cephalic area)—, the patellar spine formulae —prolateral spines in patellae I and II in *N. fagei*, in contrast to prolateral spines in the palps and leg II patellae in *N. bonali* sp. nov. Unfortunately, it is not possible to provide differences related to the spermathecae because the author did not

dissect the two specimens used for the description. However, the burrow was described in enough detail to warrant comparison with *N. bonali* sp. nov. The device used to plug the burrow by *N. fagei* is covered by a dense layer of silk, has the shape of a spatula in one end, is conical on the other end, and hangs from the burrow wall (see Frade & Bacelar, 1931; Bacelar, 1937), forming part of the silk lining of the wall, while the burrow-plugging device of *N. bonali* sp. nov. is similar to a rugby ball, is covered with little silk and is attached to the entrance of the burrow with a thin thread. The resting position of the device is also different; in *N. fagei* it hangs from the wall whereas in *N. bonali* sp. nov. it is deposited in a hollow (Fig. 2D). Additionally, the burrow entrance drawn in Frade & Bacelar (1931) for *N. fagei* is simple, while that of

Fig. 2. Spermathecae and burrow of *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. **A.** Spermathecae, ventral view. **B.** Spermathecae, frontal view. **C.** Spermathecae, dorsal view. **D.** Burrow scheme. Scale: 0.5 mm.

Fig. 2. Espermateca y madriguera de *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. **A.** Espermateca, vista ventral. **B.** Espermateca, vista frontal. **C.** Espermateca, vista dorsal. **D.** Esquema de la madriguera. Escala: 0.5 mm.

N. bonali sp. nov. includes a turret of plant debris similar as in *N. amicitia* Pertegal & Molero-Baltanás, 2022 (Fig. 2D).

ETYMOLOGY

This species is dedicated in honour of Dr. Raúl Bonal Andrés, University Professor in the Universidad Complutense de Madrid, spider enthusiast and friend.

TYPE MATERIAL

Holotype. PORTUGAL: ♀; Algarve, Alvor; 37.120525, -8.564457; 27 Sep. 2023; Cristian Pertegal leg.; MNHNC:MB09:004302.

Paratypes. PORTUGAL: 5 ♀♀ (in addition, three immatures); Algarve, Portimão; 37.173450, -8.528514; 25 Sep. 2023; Cristian Pertegal leg.; MNHNC:MB09:004303, ccpp-0513, ccpp-0514, ccpp-0515, ccpp-0516. – 3 ♀♀; Algarve, Alvor; 37.120525, -8.564457; 27 Sep. 2023; ccpp-0517, ccpp-0519, ccpp-0520.

DESCRIPTION

Female (holotype, see Fig 3)

General appearance. In vivo brownish orange colour with brown opisthosoma (Fig. 3A). Carapace slightly covered with light pubescence and with a dark medal-shaped mark on the centre of the cephalic area of the prosoma and a lighter spot on each cheek (Fig. 3B) side of the ocular process. In alcohol, pale yellow on the lighter areas of the prosoma with dark edges. The collected specimens differ in the shape and darkness of the central mark. Palps and legs pale yellow and grey. Opisthosoma with some spots drawing four-five ill-defined chevrons (Fig. 3B), yellow on its ventral side and with some dark dots.

Prosoma. Clypeus dark with a marginal row of seven bristles. POP black and divided by three light stripes, one between AME and the others on each side of AME (Fig. 3D). Caput elevated (Fig. 6C). Crest zone dark with three rows of bristles, the middle one with six well developed bristles. Fovea with a deep and curved groove. Chelicerae dark brown with light proximal area. Chericeral rastellum with four strong spikes. Fang ridge serrated. Cheliceral furrow with five-six promarginal teeth and three rows of mesodenticles. Maxillae brownish yellow with two teeth-shaped or cone-shaped cuspules on the left and four on the right. Labium as maxillae in colour. Sternum yellowish with six poorly visible sigilla, the proximal pair circular and on the edge of the sternum, the central pair somewhat more elongated than the first pair and also on the edge, and the third pair circle-shaped and near the edge (Fig. 3E).

Palp and legs yellowish with dense scopula on the palp tarsus and metatarsus becoming less dense on the tibia and on legs I and II; legs III and IV without scopula. MTF4 ratio: Ti>Fe>Met.

Prolateral and retrolateral spination. Palp, retrolateral-side: Pa: 1 (0). 1(0); Ti: 1(2). 2(1). Leg II, prolateral side: Pa: 0(1). 0(1); Ti: 1(0-1-2). 2(0-1-2); Met: 1(0). 1(0). Leg III, prolateral side: Met: 2.2; and retrolateral side: Ti: 2.2; Met: 3.3. Leg IV, prolateral side: Met: 3 (0-2). 2(0); and retrolateral side: Ti: 0(2). 0(2); Met:3.3.

Patellar spine formulae, variations (6). PSP [p: 1(0). 1(0); I: 0. 0; II: 1(0). 1(0); III: 0.0; IV: 0.0]. RSP [p: 0. 0; I: 0. 0; II: 0. 0; III: 0.0; IV: 0.0].

Opisthosoma. Spinneret morphology: PLS, proximal segment longer than the medial and distal segment together. Maculae present on the basal segment — poorly visible in some specimens. PMS finger shaped (Fig. 3G). Spermathecae: funnel-shaped with a ring of glandular tissue and globous distal end (Fig. 3F).

Measurements (mm). BL+ch: 15.87 (15.53–18); Bl: 13.4 (13.4–15.59). Prosoma; dorsal side; Ca: 3.61 (3.57–4.04); CL: 6.14 (6.09–6.96); CW: 4.67 (4.59–4.96); FR: 1.32 (1.32–1.41); Cir: 0.912 (0.9001–0.9148); Ch: 2.17 (2.14–2.71); Th: 1.13 (1.13–1.6); Cly: 0.14 (0.14–0.16); AER: 1.03 (1.03–1.16); PER: 1.05 (1.04–1.16); ALE: 0.28 (0.28–0.36); PLE: 0.27 (0.22–0.29); AME: 0.2 (0.16–0.27); PME: 0.19 (0.17–0.22); EI: 0.52 (0.52–0.57). Prosoma; ventral side; mal: 2.04 (1.87–2.15); maw: 1.25 (1.11–1.33); lal: 0.78 (0.61–0.78); law: 1.01 (0.92–1.27); stl: 3.29 (2.57–3.86); stw: 2.47 (2.35–3.68). Spermatheca; spwt: 0.15 (0.14–0.2); spwing: 0.05 (0.04–0.05); spwm: 0.14 (0.13–0.16); splenght: 0.25 (0.23–0.31); spdistint: 0.39 (0.36–0.6); spdistext: 1.03 (0.8–1.13). Palp; Tal: 1.83 (1.83–2.25); Til: 1.99 (1.88–2.17); Pal: 1.78 (1.78–1.98); Fel: 3.11 (3.11–3.66); TOTAL: 8.71 (8.71–9.86). Leg I; Tal: 1.36 (1.36–1.52); Mel: 2.26 (2.25–2.78); Til: 3.08 (2.76–3.17); Pal: 2.66 (2.63–3.03); Fel: 4.01 (3.94–4.84); TOTAL: 13.37 (13.2–15.05). Leg II; Tal: 1.22 (1.22–1.54); Mel: 1.91 (1.91–2.15); Til: 2.5 (2.41–2.62); Pal: 2.4 (2.36–2.69); Fel: 3.68 (3.6–4.17); TOTAL: 11.71 (11.71–13.03). Leg III; Tal: 1.15 (1.15–1.6); Mel: 1.82 (1.82–2.32); Til: 1.89 (1.89–2.29); Pal: 1.98 (1.98–2.31); Fel: 3.2 (3.2–3.62); TOTAL: 10.04 (10.04–11.97). Leg IV; Tal: 1.52 (1.36–1.81); Mel: 3.3 (3.3–3.8); Til: 5.19 (4.47–5.22); Pal: 2.8 (2.8–3.33); Fel: 4.15 (4.15–4.66); TOTAL: 16.96 (16.96–18.18).

INTRASPECIFIC VARIABILITY

The intraspecific variation observed in the sample involves the shape of the carapace pattern (Fig. 4), but the burrows of all specimens collected (and other specimens found but not collected) followed the same scheme.

ECOLOGY

The two localities where this species was found have different coloured clay habitats and soils. The

Fig. 3. *Nemesia bonali* sp. n. Holotype. **A.** Alive. **B.** Preserved. **C.** Carapace, lateral view. Arrows indicate the lack of a flat area on the caput and the inclination of the posterior area of caput. **D.** Eye group. **E.** Maxillae, labium and sternum. **F.** Spermathecae. **G.** Spinnerets. Scales: A–C = 5 mm; D, F–G = 0.5 mm; E = 2.5 mm.

Fig. 3. *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. Holotipo. **A.** Vivo. **B.** En alcohol. **C.** Vista lateral del prosoma. Las flechas indican el área plana en el área cefálica y su inclinación. **D.** Grupo ocular. **E.** Maxilas, labio y esternón. **F.** Espermateca. **G.** Hileras. Escalas: A–C = 5 mm; D, F–G = 0.5 mm; E = 2.5 mm.

population from Portimão inhabits an open grassland with wild olive trees and low density of vegetation cover on grey soil. This area is close to a dry marsh, likely a temporary wetland. The second population was found in cliffs with high humidity levels from the sea influence in Alvor, on the roots of *Olea europaea* L., and *Pistacia lentiscus* L., with some herbaceous plant species on a reddish soil (Fig. 5A).

The burrow built by both populations of *N. bonali* sp. nov. follows the same general structure, a flexible wafer-type lid built with soil particles and plant debris

over a tower of the same materials as the lid and a curved burrow (Fig. 5B–C). The tunnel measures about 15 cm from the edge of the entrance to the end, where the spider accumulates prey debris—ants and small beetles—. In the first section of the burrow there is a hole where a rugby ball-shaped device made of soil material sits while the burrow is unplugged. This piece is poorly covered by silk and attached to the entrance by a thin thread (Fig. 5D). The spider uses the rugby ball-shaped piece to plug the entrance to the burrow when its trapdoor is opened.

Fig. 4. Variation in colour carapace across *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. specimens. Portimão (A–C) and Alvor (D–F).

Fig. 4. Variación en el color del caparazón de los ejemplares de *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. de Portimão (A–C) y Alvor (D–F).

Fig. 5. *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. **A.** Habitat in Alvor, Portugal. **B.** Closed burrow. **C.** Opened burrow with the plug blocking the entrance. **D.** Plug.

Fig. 5. *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov. **A.** Hábitat en Alvor, Portugal. **B.** Madriguera cerrada. **C.** Madriguera abierta con el tapón en la entrada. **D.** Tapón.

***Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov.**

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Figs 6–9

DIAGNOSIS

Nemesia molerobaltanasi sp. nov. presents a unique combination of characteristics such as the shape of the spermatheca, the prosoma morphology and the spinnerets. The spermatheca is a short and columnar structure that widens before the duct ends (Fig. 6A–B). The glandular tissue covers the middle area of the spermatheca. The prosoma is longer than wider, with black margins and a dark mark in the centre covering the cephalic area and the centre of the prosoma. Finally, the spinnerets often have maculae on the PLS, and the PMS is finger shaped. The species with which it could be more easily confused is *N. ungoliant*, because of the similar shape of spermathecae—but at close inspection, the end of the duct of *N. ungoliant* seems to be irregular. Additionally, there are differences in size—*N. molerobaltanasi* with a range of 8.09–9.97 mm of body length is much smaller than

N. ungoliant with 17.7–20.9 mm—and in the shape of the carapace—more circular than rectangular in the figure of *N. ungoliant* in Decae *et al.* (2007). *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. builds a slender tower on the ground with an internal plug like *N. bonali* sp. nov. and *N. fagei* but with a teardrop shape, sitting in the basal part of the burrow and hanging from a silk thread from the burrow wall (Fig. 6C). These burrow characters allow differentiating *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. from the other two species. Other species that builds towers of soil particles on the ground is *N. qarthadasth* Calvo-García, 2021, but its burrow has two entrances and no plug and are morphologically different in the shape of spermathecae—truncheon-shaped in *N. qarthadasth*—, the patellar spine formula—*N. qarthadasth* with two prolateral spines on patella III—, the size of PMS—proportionally longer in *N. qarthadasth* than in *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov.—, and the absence of maculae on the proximal segment of PLS of *N. qarthadasth*. The two new species can be morphologically distinguished by their size—*N. bonali* sp. nov. is larger than *N. molerobaltanasi*

Fig. 6. Spermathecae and burrow of *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. **A.** Spermathecae, ventral view. **B.** Spermathecae, frontal view. **C.** Burrow scheme. Scale: 0.5 mm.

Fig. 6. Espermateca y madriguera de *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. **A.** Espermateca, vista ventral. **B.** Espermateca, vista frontal. **C.** Esquema de la madriguera. Escala: 0.5mm.

sp. nov.—, the carapace shape —more circular in *N. bonali* sp. nov. than in *N. moleroaltanasi* sp. nov.—, the morphology of spermathecae —*N. bonali* sp. nov. with funnel-shaped spermathecae with a ring in the middle of each duct vs. the columnar-shaped spermathecae of *N. moleroaltanasi* sp. nov.—, and the spine distribution on the legs.

ETYMOLOGY

This species is dedicated in honour of Dr. Rafael Molero Baltanás, University Professor at the Universidad de Córdoba, a great mentor and friend.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

Holotype. PORTUGAL: ♀; Loulé, Castelão; 37.177570, -8.084661; 29 Sep 2023; Cristian Pertegal leg.; MNHC:MB09:004304.

Paratypes. PORTUGAL: 6 ♀♀ (in addition, one immature); same data as for holotype; ccpp-0523, ccpp-0524, ccpp-0525, ccpp-0526, MNHC:MB09:004305, ccpp-0528.

DESCRIPTION

Female (holotype, see Fig. 7)

General appearance. Alive specimens are brownish orange colour with dark marks in the prosoma and the opisthosoma, more visible in alcohol (Fig. 7A–B). Carapace slightly covered by pubescence, with black margins, and the centre and caput dark brown. The distal area of the prosoma is light coloured. Opisthosoma grey, dorsally with six darker brownish chevrons (Fig. 7B).

Prosoma. Clypeus dark with a light line between the ocular process and the frontal edge and a row of nine bristles. POP black and covering separately each eye (Fig. 7D). Caput elevated (Fig. 7C). Crest zone with two light stripes and three rows of bristles, the middle one with seven gross bristles. Fovea with a deep and somewhat recurved groove. Chelicerae black with a dorsal light stain in the insertion area. Cheliceral rastellum with four strong spikes. Fang ridges serrated. Cheliceral furrow with six promarginal teeth and one-two rows of mesodenticles. Maxillae yellowish with four cone-shaped cuspules in each maxilla. Labium brown. Sternum yellowish with circular and small almost imperceptible sigilla, with different size and position, the first and the second pairs smaller than the third pair and positioned on the edge of the sternum (Fig. 7E).

Palp and legs yellowish with scopulae on the palp tarsus, and on the tarsus and metatarsus of legs I and II. MTF4 ratio: tibia>femur>metatarsus.

Prolateral and retrolateral spination. Palp, prolateral side: Ti: 2(1). 2. Leg II, prolateral side: Pa: 0(1). 0(1); Met: 2(1). 2(1). Leg III, prolateral side Met: 2(1). 2(1); and retrolateral side: Ti: 1.1; Met: 2.2. Leg IV,

prolateral side: Tibia 0(1). 0(1); Met: 2(1). 2(0-1), and retrolateral side: Ti: 0(1). 0(1); Met: 2(1). 1(2).

Patellar spine formulae, variations (6). PSP [p: 0.0; I: 0. 0; II: 0(1). 0(1); III: 0.0; IV: 0.0]. RSP [p: 0. 0; I: 0. 0; II: 0. 0; III: 0.0; IV: 0.0].

Opisthosoma. Spinneret morphology: PLS, proximal segment longer than the central and distal segments together. Maculae absent —clearly observed in three of five specimens. PMS finger shaped (Fig. 7G). Spermathecae: similar to a column with the end of duct a bit widened, glandular tissue restricted to the middle of spermatheca (Fig. 7F).

Measurements (mm). BL+ch: 9.97 (8.09–9.97); Bl: 8.07 (7.00–8.4). Prosoma; dorsal side; Ca: 2.02 (1.84–2.07); CL: 3.24 (2.97–3.41); CW: 2.45 (1.9–2.45); Ch: 1.23 (1.01–1.36); Th: 0.82 (0.5–0.82); Cir: 0.86 (0.86–0.88); Cly: 0.09 (0.06–0.09); AER: 0.65 (0.57–0.65); PER: 0.65 (0.57–0.65); ALE: 0.21 (0.15–0.21); PLE: 0.15 (0.14–0.18); AME: 0.15 (0.12–0.15); PME: 0.11 (0.09–0.11); w: 0.33 (0.29–0.35). Prosoma; ventral side; mal: 1.10 (0.93–1.1); maw: 0.69 (0.59–0.69); lal: 0.51 (0.31–0.51); law: 0.65 (0.53–0.65); stl: 1.98 (1.23–1.98); stw: 1.43 (1.24–1.77). Spermatheca; spwt: 0.1 (0.08–0.1); spwm: 0.09 (0.06–0.1); splenght: 0.15 (0.12–0.15); spdistint: 0.31 (0.24–0.32); spdistext: 0.51 (0.44–0.64). Palp; Tal: 1.13 (1–1.17); Til: 1.09 (0.81–1.09); Pal: 1.03 (0.81–1.03); Fel: 1.69 (1.29–1.69); TOTAL P: 4.94 (4.01–4.94). Leg I; Tal: 0.95 (0.75–0.95); Mel: 1.29 (1.06–1.29); Til: 1.75 (1.5–1.75); Pal: 1.38 (1.17–1.51); Fel: 2.12 (1.94–2.25); TOTAL I: 7.49 (6.62–7.49). Leg II; Tal: 0.85 (0.74–0.85); Mel: 1.12 (0.98–1.12); Til: 1.52 (1.17–1.52); Pal: 1.28 (1.14–1.28); Fel: 1.95 (1.75–1.95); TOTAL II: 6.72 (5.91–6.72). Leg III; Tal: 0.85 (0.66–0.85); Mel: 1.08 (0.91–1.08); Til: 1.11 (0.88–1.11); Pal: 1.03 (0.95–1.12); Fel: 1.64 (1.45–1.64); TOTAL III: 5.71 (4.96–5.71). Leg IV; Tal: 0.80 (0.62–0.8); Mel: 1.71 (1.39–1.71); Til: 3.04 (2.68–3.04); Pal: 1.85 (1.48–1.85); Fel: 1.74 (1.74–2.03); TOTAL IV: 9.14 (8.35–9.14).

INTRASPECIFIC VARIABILITY

The presence of maculae on the PLS is variable, but in the sample, they are more frequently present than absent (Fig. 8).

ECOLOGY

Nemesia moleroaltanasi sp. nov. was found on the slopes on either side of a road in the town of Loulé. The vegetation is composed by crops of *Olea europaea* with some specimens of *Quercus suber* L. and some herbaceous plants. The burrow of this species is characteristic. The spider builds a first section with the shape of a slender tower on the surface of the ground with a rigid wafer-type trapdoor at the edge of the entrance. The burrow section on the ground is a thin tunnel with a widening end, in the shape of a chamber (Fig. 9A–C). A teardrop-shaped piece of clay hangs with a thin thread from the wall (Fig. 9C–D).

Fig. 7. *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. Holotipo. **A.** Alive. **B.** Preserved. **C.** Carapace, lateral view. Arrows indicate the lack of a flat area on the caput and the inclination of the posterior area of caput. **D.** Eye group. **E.** Maxillae, labium and sternum. **F.** Spermathecae. **G.** Spinnerets. Scales: A–B = 5 mm; C, E = 1 mm; D, G = 0.5 mm; F = 0.1 mm.

Fig. 7. *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. Holotipo. **A.** Vivo. **B.** En alcohol. **C.** Vista lateral del prosoma. Las flechas indican el área plana en el área cefálica y su inclinación. **D.** Grupo ocular. **E.** Maxilas, labio y esternón. **F.** Espermateca. **G.** Hileras. Escalas: A–B = 5 mm; C, E = 1 mm; D, G = 0.5 mm; F = 0.1 mm.

The widest section of this piece fits into the narrower section of the burrow, and the spider uses this piece to isolate the safe chamber at the bottom from the narrower section. At the time of sampling, three adult females had about 10 offspring in the chamber.

***Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov.**

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Figs 10–13

DIAGNOSIS

The general shape of spermathecae of *N. rebellis* sp. nov. seems to be intermediate between those of the two previously described new species, characterized by the globular end of receptacles and the absence of a middle ring of glandular tissue (Fig. 10A–B). The crest zone of *N. rebellis* sp. nov. has a smooth area between the dorsal bristles and the ocular tubercle, a feature lacking in the other two species, and its distal area is also more inclined than that of the other species. *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. is slightly larger than *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. —11.39–13.39 mm of body size range vs. 9.97–10.09 mm, respectively—, and smaller than *N. bonali* sp. nov. —11.00–15.53 mm—. In this aspect, this third new species is within the range of body sizes presented

by Decae *et al.* (2007) for *N. fagei*: —between 11.5 and 17.2 mm—, but several differences are found in their morphology. *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. is different from *N. fagei* by the lack of the ring in their spermathecae and their globular end of ducts, the high elevation of cephalic area, the presence of the smooth section in the crest and the present of maculae in PLS. As for the burrow and the plug made by *N. rebellis* sp. nov., the entrance and the first section are tight, and the general orientation of the burrow is horizontal (Fig. 10C). The plug —with one end shaped like an elongated tight spatula and the other as a tear drop— is positioned in the middle section of the burrow and attached to the wall of the gallery by a thin tread. All these characteristics differ from the burrow of *N. fagei*, which has a vertical orientation, a plug with one end as a wide spatula and the other end as a bullet —see Frade & Bacelar (1931)—, and this plug is part of the wall of the burrow —see Decae (1996). The differences with the other two new species are the shape of the plug, the orientation of the burrow, the disposition of the plug inside the gallery, and the external buildings of each species.

ETYMOLOGY

Fig. 8. Variation in maculae presence on PLS across *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. individuals.

Fig. 8. Variación en la presencia de máculas en PLS en los ejemplares de *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov.

Fig. 9. **A.** A small patch with *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. burrows from Loulé, Portugal. **B.** Opened burrow with the plug blocking the entrance. **C.** Plug **D.** Blocked section of burrow.

Fig. 9. **A.** Pequeño parche de madrigueras de *Nemesia molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. en Loulé, Portugal. **B.** Madriguera abierta. **C.** Tapón. **D.** Sección taponada de la madriguera.

The species typically builds the aperture of its burrow against the wall of the slope, in contrast to the usual and “logical” entrances of other *Nemesia* species. For this reason, it is considered a “rebellious” species for not adhering to typical behaviour patterns.

The name corresponds to the Latin adjective “*rebellis*”, which means “rebellious”.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

Fig. 10. Spermathecae and burrow of *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. **A.** Spermathecae, ventral view. **B.** Spermathecae, frontal view. **C.** Burrow scheme. Scale: 0.5 mm.

Fig. 10. Espermateca y madriguera de *N. rebellis* sp. nov. **A.** Espermateca, vista ventral. **B.** Espermateca, vista frontal. **C.** Esquema de la madriguera. Escala: 0.5mm.

Holotype. PORTUGAL: ♀; Odeleite; 37.322378, -7.580936; 2 May 2024; Cristian Pertegal & Irene Reina leg.; MNHNC: MB09:004307.

Paratypes. PORTUGAL: 5 ♀♀ (in addition, four immatures); same data as for holotype; MNHNC: MB09:004308, ccpp-0553, ccpp-0554, ccpp-0555, ccpp-0556.

DESCRIPTION

Female (holotype, see Fig 11)

General appearance. Orange-brown in colour with a faint central mark on the prosoma and transversal dark markings on the opisthosoma when alive, but yellowish with more pronounced markings when preserved in alcohol (Fig. 11A–B). Carapace with low pubescence cover, black margins, dark brown centre and caput, and a light stain in the ocular area. Opisthosoma grey-yellow with four to five dark dorsal chevrons (Fig. 11B).

Prosoma. Clypeus slightly projected over chelicerae and dark with a row of five bristles. POP divided in three black dots (Fig. 11D). Caput elevated with a fairly steep slope from the fovea to the cephalic zone and a flat area between the crest zone and the ocular group (Fig. 11C). Crest zone with three rows of bristles, the middle one with seven gross bristles. Fovea and all characters of the Chelicerae as described for *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. Maxillae brown-yellowish with four-five (six in some specimens) cone-shaped cuspules. Labium brown. Sternum brown-yellowish with elongated and poorly visible sigilla, (Fig. 11E).

Palp and legs as in *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov.

Prolateral and retrolateral spination. Palp, prolateral side: Ti: 2 (1-3). 2.(1); Ta: 1(0).0(0). Leg II, prolateral side: Pa: 1(2). 0(1-2); Ti: 0(1-2).1(0); Met: 1. 1. Leg III, prolateral side Met: 2. 2(1); and retrolateral side: Ti: 2(1).1(2); Met: 3(2).3(1). Leg IV, prolateral side: Met: 1. 0(1), and retrolateral side: Ti: 0(1). 0(1); Met: 2(3). 3.

Patellar spine formulae, variations (6). PSP [p: 0(1).0; I: 0. 0; II: 1(0).0(2); III: 0.0; IV: 0.0]. RSP [p: 0. 0; I: 0. 0; II: 0. 0; III: 0.0; IV: 0.0].

Opisthosoma. Spinneret morphology: PLS as previous new species. Maculae present (Fig. 11G). PMS finger shaped. Spermathecae: flattened in the first section with a globous or spheric end (Fig. 11F).

Measurements (mm). Bl+ch: 13.39 (11.39–13.39); Bl: 11.69 (9.98–11.69). Prosoma; dorsal side; Ca: 2.83 (2.53–3.08); CL: 4.73 (4.13–5.27); CW: 3.48 (2.95–3.78); Ch: 1.75 (1.41–1.75); Th: 0.96 (0.75–1.04); Cir: 0.89 (0.87); Cly: 0.3 (0.13–0.3); AER: 0.85 (0.71–0.97); PER: 0.89 (0.75–0.99); ALE: 0.23 (0.21–0.28); PLE: 0.27 (0.19–0.27); AME: 0.13 (0.11–0.13); PME: 0.15 (0.12–0.16); l: 0.46 (0.38–0.51). Prosoma; ventral side; mal: 1.42 (0.9–1.54); maw: 0.93 (0.83–1.42); lal: 0.45 (0.4–0.53); law: 0.84 (0.71–0.88); stl: 2.56 (2.33–3.02); stw: 1.84 (1.74–1.96). Spermatheca; spwt: 0.12

(0.12–0.14); spwm: 0.14 (0.12–0.15); splengt: 0.22 (0.2–0.22); spdistint: 0.39 (0.31–0.43); spdistext: 0.7 (0.67–0.97) Palp; Tal: 1.46 (1.27–1.66); Til: 1.47 (1.3–1.49); Pal: 1.49 (1.17–1.49); Fel: 2.55 (2.04–2.55); TOTAL P: 6.97 (5.82–6.97). Leg I; Tal: 1.2 (0.74–1.37); Mel: 1.85 (1.53–1.93); Til: 2.39 (1.84–2.52); Pal: 2.05 (1.72–2.25); Fel: 3.13 (2.76–3.73); TOTAL I: 10.62 (9.03–11.8). Leg II; Tal: 0.97 (0.92–1.09); Mel: 1.49 (1.31–1.85); Til: 1.81 (1.69–2.1); Pal: 1.9 (1.44–2.06); Fel: 2.73 (2.33–3.07); TOTAL II: 8.9 (7.73–10.15). Leg III; Tal: 1.02 (0.91–1.1); Mel: 1.56 (1.37–1.74); Til: 1.42 (1.25–1.63); Pal: 1.73 (1.38–1.73); Fel: 2.22 (1.76–2.36); TOTAL III: 7.95 (6.72–8.51). Leg IV; Tal: 1.15 (0.98–1.17); Mel: 2.54 (2.21–2.71); Til: 3.9 (3.47–3.9); Pal: 2.49 (2.26–2.72); Fel: 3.05 (2.44–3.39); TOTAL IV: 13.13 (11.45–13.72).

INTRASPECIFIC VARIABILITY

The intraspecific variations found in *N. rebellis* sp. nov. are in the opisthosoma drawn definition and the shape of clypeus (Fig. 12). Only one specimen revised—including all immatures—lacks the smooth area in the crest.

ECOLOGY

These spiders were found on slopes in Odeleite where it shared habitats with *Iberesia machadoi* (Decae & Cardoso, 2006) and *Ummidia algarve* (Decae, 2010). The area is covered by pine forest mixed with patches of holm oaks, cork oaks, olives, and other crops. *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. usually builds a burrow with the entrance door against the wall of the slope. This entrance can be slightly elevated, a few millimetres above the surface of the soil, and is narrow compared to the distal half of the burrow — where the spider accumulates remains of prey, such as ants. The spider blocks the middle of the burrow with a plug, which has the shape of a spatula in the first end and the shape of a tear drop in the other end. This plug is attached to the wall of the gallery (Fig. 13).

It is not possible to offer any data about the phenology of the species because offspring or mature males were not observed.

Statistical analysis

The circularity of the prosoma was best modelled using only species identity (AIC: -104.4732), which was highly significant. Among the species, *N. bonali* sp. nov. showed higher circularity than *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. and *N. rebellis* sp. nov. (Table 2; Fig. 14).

Table 2. Significance test. Significance code: 0 ****.

Tabla 2. Test de significancia. Código de significancia: 0 ****.

Fig. 11. *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. Holotype. **A.** Alive. **B.** Preserved. **C.** Carapace, lateral view. Arrows indicate the flat area on the caput and the inclination of the posterior area of caput. **D.** Eye group. **E.** Maxillae, labium and sternum. **F.** Spermathecae. **G.** Spinnerets. Scales: A–B = 5 mm; C, E = 1 mm; D, G = 0.5 mm; F = 0.1 mm.

Fig. 11. *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. Holotipo. **A.** Vivo. **B.** En alcohol. **C.** Vista lateral del prosoma. Las flechas indican el área plana en el área cefálica y su inclinación. **D.** Grupo ocular. **E.** Maxilas, labio y esternón. **F.** Espermateca. **G.** Hileras. Escalas: A–B = 5 mm; C, E = 1 mm; D, G = 0.5 mm; F = 0.1 mm.

Response: Circularity

LR	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)
Species	71278	2	3.328e-16 ***

DiscussionTHE CHALLENGING IDENTIFICATION OF *NEMESIA FAGEI*

Several inconsistencies have been observed in the literature regarding the morphological characteristics and burrow description of *N. fagei*. First, several morphological characters differ when comparing the

original description with the redescription by Decae *et al.* (2007). Specimens described in the redescription are smaller than specimens in the original description—3.7–5.2 mm of carapace length in specimens in the revision—, the caput presents different elevation—slightly elevated in the revision and very elevated in the original description— and the formula for patellar spines—spines present only on the prolateral surface of patella IV in the revision, and spines present in the prolateral surfaces of patella I and II in the original description. Other differences were found in the burrow descriptions. In the original description, Frade & Bacelar (1931) commented that the burrow

Fig. 12. Variation in clypeus shape across *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. individuals.

Fig. 12. Variación en la forma del clipeo en diferentes ejemplares de *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov.

plug of this species has one end like a spatula and the other like a bullet. Bacelar (1937) described, using drawings and photographs, three additional burrows that differed from the original description. One had a plug with the shape of a rugby-ball ending. The second one, described by Mr Hughe Main in a letter sent to her, shows that some burrows may have their entrance raised above the surface of the soil. Finally, a picture provided by Bacelar (1937: pl. LXXIX) seems to correspond to the last section of the burrow

of *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov., with the difference that the proximal end of the plug in the new species has no dense silk. Because of the absence of the first section of the burrow in the image, it is impossible to be sure if this burrow belongs to *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. or *N. rebellis* sp. nov.

On the other hand, four female specimens from the collection of the Museum of Paris were examined, referenced as AR497, Buc 59-62, Buc 65-62, and Buc 77-61, based on pictures of the dorsal-view

Fig. 13. Trapdoor and plug of *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. **A.** Closed burrow. **B.** Opened burrow. **C.** Plug.

Fig. 13. Trampilla y tapón de *Nemesia rebellis* sp. nov. **A.** Madriguera cerrada. **B.** Madriguera abierta. **C.** Tapón.

and spermathecae provided by the museum. The only specimen with spermathecae was AR497; the remaining specimens lacked copulatory organs. The morphology and spermathecae of AR497 appear similar to those of *N. bonali* sp. nov. but the locality is unknown. The specimens identified as “*N. fagei* var. *major*” by Buchli (1969) —Buc 59-62 and Buc 65-62— exhibit a similar body shape to that of *N. bonali* sp. nov., and the locality where they were collected, near Alvor and Portimão (Peninha), is consistent with assignment to this species. Conversely, the specimen Buc 77-61, identified as “*N. fagei* var. *minor*” by Buchli, should be identified as *N. af. fagei*, pending future verification of the type of burrow constructed by this population from Albufeira. However, the absence of data regarding the burrows where they were found makes any identification tentative. The more conservative identifications would be *N. af. fagei* 1 for “*N. fagei* var. *major*” and *N. af. fagei* 2 for “*N. fagei* var. *minor*”, to clarify that these are different species from *N. fagei*, though possibly related, and not variations of that species.

INFERRING ECOLOGICAL AND BEHAVIORAL INFORMATION FROM MORPHOLOGICAL TRAITS

The circularity of the carapace —and maybe other morphological characters— could have a close relationship with how the spider moves inside the burrow and the different strategies of hunting or defense. Elongated carapaces, as those identified in *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. and *N. rebellis* sp. nov., are generally associated to fossorial lifestyles and with moving in one-way direction along the burrows, as observed in members of the Holarctic spider family Segestriidae Simon, 1893, which representatives have elongated carapace and even legs I to III facing forward. In contrast, the circular carapace observed in *N. bonali* sp. nov. could be associated with a less constrained space within the burrow that would allow the spider to move more freely.

The study of the structure of the burrows, as well as other aspects of behavior, has called the interest of experts in the study of trap-door spiders for over a century. For example, Moggridge (1873, 1874) described the burrow structure of several trapdoor spider species, which helped distinguishing the species known at the time by providing detailed descriptions and drawings of their burrows. The lack of burrow descriptions can potentially lead to misidentifications, and morphological differences among populations

Fig. 14. Difference in the carapace circularity of *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov., *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. and *N. rebellis* sp. nov.

Fig. 14. Diferencia en la circularidad del caparazón entre *Nemesia bonali* sp. nov., *N. molerobaltanasi* sp. nov. y *N. rebellis* sp. nov.

could be mistakenly considered to represent intraspecific variation. An example of this is *N. uncinata* Bacelar, 1937. This species was redescribed by Decae *et al.* (2007), on the basis of specimens collected by pitfall traps in different localities in Portugal, but the authors did not provide details about the burrows. The species has been recorded from several localities in the southwestern Iberian peninsula, including some areas of Cádiz, Spain. These last Spanish populations were characterised by Pertegal & Molero-Baltanás (2022), with descriptions of the burrows and detailing the differences in morphology found between the populations of Algarve, Portugal and Cádiz, Spain. The detailed morphological descriptions provided in their work is sufficient to consider the Cádiz population as a previously overlooked new species (*in prep.*). *Nemesia uncinata* may thus be an endemic species of the Algarve (Decae pers. comm.), —where it coexists with another species closely related to *Nemesia dorthesi* Thorell, 1975, which could be easily mistaken for *N. uncinata* (pers. obs)—, therefore, records outside this area should be regarded with caution and considered as potential misidentifications.

In conclusion, several considerations should be taken into account when studying the taxonomy and biology of Iberian *Nemesia*: (i) the structure of the burrow may provide essential traits for the diagnosis of the species (Mora, 2015: 31, 76, 304); (ii) the genus *Nemesia*, as other mygalomorph spiders, shows a very conservative morphology (Buchli, 1969; Bond *et al.*, 2006), which constitutes a challenge for species identification, (iii) because of its complex geological and climate history and heterogeneous geography, the Iberian peninsula constitutes a biodiversity hotspot with a high level of endemism (Ortuño & Martínez-Pérez, 2011), (iv) *Nemesia* species evolution and distribution may have been affected by the type of soil where they dwell, as already reported in other ground-dwelling microhabitat arachnid specialists, such as Solifugae (Brookhart & Muma, 1981; Griffin, 1998; Valdivia *et al.*, 2011; Hebets *et al.*, 2023) or wolf spiders, where the type of soil could have influenced different biological features such as the evolution of courtship communication (Elias *et al.*, 2004, 2010; Hebets *et al.*, 2008, 2013, 2021, 2023; Starrett *et al.*, 2022). For all these reasons, all records based solely on morphological identification should be taken with great caution, especially those whose specimens are found hundreds of kilometres away from the site of the original description, suggesting a strong discontinuity in the distribution. It is improbable to find the same species at such distances given the limited dispersal abilities of mygalomorph spiders (e.g., *Promyrmekiaphila korematsui*, Starrett *et al.* 2024). Detailed morphological and burrow characterisations, along with biogeographical information, should be, therefore, routinely integrated into the description of new nemesiid taxa.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author contributions

CP conceived the ideas and designed the methodology; CP collected the data; CP analysed the data; CP and GR writing the manuscript. All authors contributed to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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